

Description of SND metadata profile

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Background

To facilitate researchers from various fields in describing and sharing data via SND's services, SND has developed a broad metadata profile that can be adopted to specific domains through so-called research areas profiles. The goal is to provide adapted research area profiles that correspond to the top-level categories of the OECD *Fields of Research and Development classification* (FORD)¹, which can also be mapped to *The Swedish standard classification of fields of research* (SSIF)². In addition, a number of profiles adapted for additional subject areas are available.

To date, up until autumn 2025 SND supports the following research area profiles³:

- Agricultural Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Engineering and Technology (broad classification in OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Medical and Health Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Natural Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Social Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Veterinary Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD and SSIF)
- History and Archaeology (second-level classification OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Earth and Related Environmental Sciences (second-level classification OECD FORD and SSIF)
- Language Resources

In addition to these profiles, a *general profile* and a profile for *simplified registration* are also offered. *Simplified Registration* is a minimal metadata profile that fulfils DataCite's requirements but complies with the FAIR principles to a limited extent. Datasets shared via *Simplified Registration* are not covered by SND's Trusted Digital Repository certification⁴.

Structure

SND's metadata framework is based on the metadata standard Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)⁵ and on DataCite's recommendations. The research area profiles also support requirements from domain-specific standards and international research infrastructures.

The foundation is SND's master profile, *SND Master*⁶, which contains all the metadata elements and their properties supported by SND's system. The underlying profiles (sub-profiles) are then based on

¹ <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/classifications/Family/Detail/1039>

² <https://www.scb.se/dokumentation/klassifikationer-och-standarder/standard-for-svensk-indelning-av-forskningsamnen/>

³ Metadata profiles for the Humanities and the Arts is planned for development and launch in 2022.

⁴ SND is certified according to the Core Trust Seal, <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>.

⁵ <https://ddialliance.org/>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6701446>

the elements that are relevant for each research area, in combination with domain-specific controlled vocabularies.

All profiles share a set of mandatory metadata elements. These elements are specified in the documentation for *SND Master*. Each sub-profile can also include additional mandatory elements, which will be specified in the documentation for the profile.

Documentation

The SND metadata profiles are documented separately, based on the documentation for *SND Master*.

Every metadata element has the following information:

ID	A unique identifier for each metadata field. The identifier is global to all profiles.
Element	The name of the metadata element, in Swedish and English.
Definition	The element definition in Swedish and English.
Allowed content	A description of which information/values are allowed for the element. For example, controlled vocabularies are written "CV: DDI".
Occurrence	The element's cardinality: 0-n = optional and repeatable 0-1 = optional, non-repeatable 1-n = mandatory and repeatable 1 = mandatory, non-repeatable
Terms	A description of whether there are specific conditions for the visibility of the element.
Comment	Further explanatory comments.

Versions

The version information refers to *SND Master*, for individual subject profiles other changes may occur.

Version 1 2022-06-23	
Version 2 2023-08-28	Deleted elements: D2, D4, D5, D6, D7, D9, D17, D18 New name (English): S16.1 New definition: S16, S25 New allowed content: S32, S37.1